

Milestone:

M3.2 Outcome of consultation on sequencing practices. A report on the status of procedures for WGS and WES across Europe will be prepared

Lead Participant:

CRG

Author:

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Due:

30 Nov 2021

Date Of Completion:

29 Nov 2021

Means of Verification

The consultation was done in preparation for deliverable D3.1, which was handed in June 2021: [B1MG D3.1 - Quality metrics for sequencing](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

KU Leuven (Belgium), FIMM Sequencing Unit (Finland), German Cancer Research Center (Germany), National Institute of Oncology (Hungary), San Camillo-Forlanini hospitals (Italy), ARC-Net Applied Research on Cancer centre at the University of Verona (Italy), Universita Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (Italy), Vilnius University Hospital Santaros Klinikos (Lithuania), Hartwig Medical Foundation (Netherlands), Radboudumc (Netherlands), Oslo University Hospital (Norway), Telemark Hospital Trust (Norway), Instituto Nacional de Saude Dr Ricardo Jorge (Portugal), University of Aveiro (Portugal), Clinical institute of Genomic Medicine (Slovenia), Carlos III Institute of Health (Spain), CNIC (Spain), Fundacion Publica Galega de Medicina Xenomica (Spain), Hospital Universitario Ramon y Cajal (Spain), Clinical Genomics, SciLifeLab (Sweden), Genomics England (United Kingdom)

Next action steps

NA

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